
William Wordsworth's Poetry's Romantic Themes

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Romantics reject morality in favor of reality and naturalism. They hold that man should enjoy what he gets from nature rather than being validated or stereotyped to one set of rules. In any case, the study of Romantic poetry's themes is not given as much attention as the idea that beauty is produced from the form of art for its own sake. For the Romantics, "nature" signified many different things; it was frequently portrayed in symbolic language as an artistic creation created by a supernatural imagination. Three poems by William Wordsworth—"My Heart Leaps up when I behold," "The World is Too Much With Us," and "The Daffodils" or "I Wandered Lonely as a Cloud". As mentioned in the methodology, these poems will be analyzed using the Romantic theory.

This research project aims to explain to the reader the essence of Romantic poetry. The researcher's goal is to critically present William Wordsworth as an emotional and romantic writer. His poetry will demonstrate the result of his creativity and feelings. He promoted human principles both politically and morally. The author advocates for intellectual freedom free from self-interest. The age of Romanticism and its effects on society are also major topics of the study. With reference to William Wordsworth, it illustrates the influence of nature on humanity.

The purpose of this research project is to demonstrate the Romantic writer's inherent nature. William Wordsworth's poetry demonstrates how a romantic writer finds contentment in withdrawing from this world and entering a different one that is filled with peace, joy, happiness, health, love, and compassion. For him, nature is the one thing that can provide him comfort. There have been studies on nature-related themes and topics, but because William Wordsworth loved nature, this study highlights the element of nature in his poetry.

WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S NATURE POETRY:

Wordsworth compared a restless quest for scientific knowledge to a contemplative, vacant, and pensive attitude. He thought that conversing with rural people or connecting with nature taught us more than reading books. He held that all goodness and truth originate from harmony with nature. The romanticists' catchphrase was nature, but in a completely different sense. The quintessential naturalist poet, William Wordsworth, was meticulous about the physical world around him, including the plants, animals, weather, and topography. William Wordsworth was a self-aware literary artist at the time, and his writings were known as Wordsworthian. Wordsworthian "nature" is a result of both his extensive reading and his contemplation of the striking Lake District scenery. He frequently answers to nature's messages in his poems by speaking on its behalf. William Wordsworth's "nature" leads us to the shaky realm of postmodern meaning and away from the closed word of ethnocentric symbol of making. The Romantic era, when William Wordsworth wrote, had few regulations and allowed writers to express themselves freely. The French Revolution and the Industrial Revolution both brought about changes in this era.

EXAMINING AND TALKING ABOUT “MY HEART LEAPS UP WHEN I BEHOLD”:

The romantic poets regard nature with awe. They have a tendency to worship any natural agent they come across. The poem is a sort of sentimental remembrance since William Wordsworth exhibits this attitude when he encounters the rainbow. One stanza and nine lines make up the poem "MY HEART LEAPS UP WHEN I BEHOLD," and its succinctness adds to its potency. It takes the shape of a story poem. When the poet describes his encounter with the rainbow, he is overcome with joy and his soul is uplifted. Lines one and two illustrate this as follows:

My heart leaps up when I behold

A rainbow in the sky.

From there, he goes into a philosophical consideration of the experience saying that the rainbow like other agents of nature is permanent.

So was it when my life began

So is it now I am a man

So be it when I shall grow old

Or let me die

The same lines also suggest the ephemeral nature of man who unlike the rainbow cannot exist forever. He is born, grows old and eventually dies.

The child is the father of man

And I could wish my days to be

Bound each by natural piety

The same poet would address this penchant for worldliness in another poem, "The World Is Too Much with Us." The final suggestion made by the poet personae is that man should acquire a deep reverence for nature from his early years.

ROMANTIC ELEMENTS IN THE POEM "MY HEART LEAPS UP WHEN I BEHOLD" BY WILLIAM WORDSWORTH:

The poem demonstrates the beauty of nature. The seven different colors of the rainbow are violet, indigo, blue, green, yellow, orange, and red, as demonstrated by common experience and common sense. According to some, these colors are the brightest of all. As a result, their combination is lovely and endearing. Because of its beauty, the poet is drawn to it and becomes enchanted. The poem also explores the idea of nature's persistence. A timeless phenomena is nature. It is not constrained by space or time. It never stops. The poem claims that nature possesses this attribute. It deceives people and persists from one generation to the next. The human race is a transient entity on Earth. His days are hence short and sorrowful. Nonetheless, he finds comfort in nature.

WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S "MY HEART LEAPS UP WHEN I BEHOLD" HAS THE FOLLOWING STYLES, STRUCTURES, AND FORMS:

In structure, the poem consists of a single stanza. In terms of literary form, the verse is blank because the lines are not rhymed. It is a poetic ballad as well. A lyrical ballad, according to Romantic poetry stanza, is a brief poem in which the poet conveys his or her own thoughts or emotions. The poem uses simple, rustic language. This shouldn't come as a surprise because Wordsworth indicated in the introduction to his lyrical ballad that the main goal of these poems was to select incidents and situations

from everyday life and, to the greatest extent feasible, relate or describe them using a variety of language that men actually use. The term "rainbow" is a reference or allusion found in the Bible. Because of the violence and various wicked acts, God destroyed the first world with a flood. But according to the Bible, Noah was well-liked by the Lord. The rest of the world died, but he and his family were spared. God sent the "Rainbow" after the devastation as a reminder to Noah that he would never again wipe out the world with a flood. In the poem, the rainbow is portrayed as a natural agency.

Additionally, it might be said that the poem depicts God's presence and uses its many hues to symbolize God's qualities. For example, violet can stand for God's love, just as blue can stand for God's peace and red for God's wrath. Line 1's "My Heart Leaps up When I Behold" is a prime illustration of personification. The ability to "leap" is typically attributed to a man's living body rather than the human heart. Since the heart is a metaphor for the entire human body, the phrase "leaps up" is also a phrasal verb with synecdoche. Line 7's statement, "The child is the father of man," is an illustration of a paradox. Although it originally meant that the child will eventually become a parent, the poem's context demonstrates that children are more in tune with nature than adults. Man's fleeting nature is contrasted with nature's permanence. Nature is therefore more valuable than humans. Lastly, the poet is in an exhilarating mood.

ROMANTIC ELEMENTS IN WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S "THE WORLD IS TOO MUCH WITH US":

In essence, William Wordsworth's poem is an homage and exaltation of nature. The poet asserts that nature is an important aspect of every society and ought to be admired and respected at all costs. It deserves to be handled with extreme caution, reverence, and respect. Individuals must have sufficient self-control in how they interact with nature and its resources. Given all of the advantages that society has, nature ought to be regarded as its most precious resource. It gives us the necessities of life—clothing, food, and shelter. It cares for the dead as well as the living. In actuality, it is impossible to overstate the role that nature plays in human existence. In this poem, William Wordsworth argues that rather than pursuing a closer relationship with nature, where happiness might be found, we waste a lot of energy on worldly or material possessions. According to him, living in balance and harmony with nature is the only way we may fully enjoy life. Only when we accept nature will we be able to enjoy all of its great advantages. The poet poetically puts it as thus:

The world is too much with us

Late and soon, getting and spending

We lay waste our powers, little

Did we see in nature that is ours; we have

Given our heart away a sordid boon!

The poet compares live in a rural or village

Setting in which we live in cities or urban areas. We may properly appreciate the beauty of nature because we actively pursue earthly aspirations, as Wordsworth, a romantic poet, prefers the beauty of rural lives to the fight and pursuit of monetary gains, which he refers to in the poem as "getting and spending."

This ocean, which exposes her breasts to the moon, We are out of touch with the winds that will be howling constantly and are now collected like sleeping flowers for this. The poet conveys in these lines the passionate level of nature and its romantic and fantastical vision that we are blind to. The world has a set order and was made in God's perfect image. The reason for this is that we, as the earth's occupants, are immoral and have disregarded the laws that God has established. According to the poet, "society is nature and nature is society." The poet is primarily concerned by the fact that man has given up all of nature's resources in favor of transient worldly ideals. We have utterly failed to recognize and utilize nature's blessings, such as the "winds," "sea," "moon," and "sleeping flowers." We are "out of tune" because we have not been able to live in harmony and balance with nature, which is why we lack peace, order, and stability.

It moves us not Great God! I'd rather be a pagan suckled in a

Creed out worn, so might I, standing on this pleasant lea, have

Glimpses that would make me less forlorn; have sight of Proteus

Rising from sea; or hear old triton blow his wreathed horn.

Moving on to lines 9–11, the poet declares that he would rather be a pagan with archaic beliefs than lead a life isolated from the natural world. He claims that he might stand on the "pleasant lee" (open grassland) and reflect on his dire circumstances, in which people with great talents seem so uncaring, so ungodly, and so dishonest that the poet is left with no hope and is simply too exhausted to understand

this state of affairs. The poet takes a seat in an open area to get a broad perspective of the situation. From there, he may see the sea god Proteus or hear another sea god, Triton, blowing his wreathed horn or trumpet. This poem conveys a strong, understandable, instructive message that should inspire humanity to value nature and its natural resources. We can only really appreciate nature when we are in its presence.

THE ROMANTIC LANGUAGE AND STRUCTURE OF WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S "THE WORLD IS TOO MUCH WITH US":

The poem's economical use of language makes it a sonnet, which is a poem of fourteen lines. It's a sonnet by Petrarch. It has a sextet (the final six lines) and an octave (the first eight lines). The Petrarchan rhyme scheme is used in its ABBA, ABBA, and CDCDCD rhyme schemes. The poem by William Wordsworth is written in an extremely straightforward, uncomplicated style. With the exception of a few terms like "Proteus and Triton," "lea" (line 11), "sordid boon" (line 4), and "wreathed horn" (line 11), very few words in the poem would cause difficulty for the typical reader. The reader's comprehension of the poetry is improved by the simplicity of the language. The poem's tone is grave, harsh, and abrasive, and it condemns and berates man for his disregard for and abandonment of nature. The overall attitude it conveys is one of rage, hopelessness, despair, dread, and calamity. Two examples of personification are main in the poem:

- (a) 'The sea bares her bosom to the moon'
- (b) 'the winds that will be howling at all hours'

At this point the 'sea' and the 'wind' do not have any life really but in the poem they are given human qualities. Resonance was used in the poem in

- (a) 'Bares her bosom'
- (b) 'Great God'
- (c) 'We waste'

A valuable moral lesson about human society can be learned from the poem. It is recommended that society get closer to nature. Individuals must exercise sufficient restraint with regard to nature and its resources. Only when we accept nature will we be able to enjoy all of its great advantages.

THE ROMANTIC THINGS IN WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S "THE WORLD IS TOO MUCH WITH US":

The poem discusses the interaction between nature and humans. Nature is essential to man. Seeing, hearing, and experiencing the world's freshness are all true pleasures. Nature is linked to both spiritual and physical well-being. In addition to being beautiful, the landscape and the natural world are admired for their capacity to convey some of the elusive truths and mental conceptions. The poem's failure to recognize the value of nature is another subject. Man has a lot to gain from nature, but it is regrettable that he does not value it. However, nature and man work together to create a perfect and whole environment. Man's weak justification for not appreciating nature is too commonplace and irrational. It puts man at a disadvantage. Natural elements like the sea, moon, wind, and flowers are examples of how beautiful nature is. This is one of the bio-geographical characteristics that define the world.

SUMMARY OF WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S "I WANDERED LONELY AS A CLOUD" OR "THE DAFFODILS":

The poem's events are quite straightforward, but the incident's significance is more nuanced. The poet is strolling by a lake by himself. Suddenly, he sees a field of lovely "daffodils" that are swinging in the wind. He is thrilled and ecstatic about this. The lakeside is not where the joy ends. Every other time he recalls, he transports himself back to the moment, which makes him incredibly happy.

In four stanzas, William Wordsworth tells us the specifics of this straightforward experience. In stanza 1, the poet is by himself when he unexpectedly discovers an abundance of yellow daffodils beneath the trees by a lake. They bend from side to side in response to the wind's direction:

I wandered lonely as a cloud that floats on high over vales and hills, when all at once I saw a crowd, a host of golden Daffodils

Beside the lake, beneath the trees.

The poet is overcome by the incalculable number of daffodils in stanza two. They are as many as the "stars" in the sky, a "crowd," and a "host." The poet found it hard to believe.

Fluttering and dancing in the breeze, continuous as the stars that

shine and twinkle on the Milky Way, they stretched in never ending line along the

margin of a bay.

The lake's waves likewise oscillate from side to side in stanza three due to the breeze. Nevertheless, it is more entertaining to watch the daffodils as they sway from side to side. The poet is so overcome with emotion and joy that he has no idea how long this scene will stay in his memory or how much joy it will bring him.

I gazed and gazed – but little thought what wealth the show to me had brought.

In verse four, the poet learns that he frequently remembers this sight when he is by himself, and his loneliness transforms into joy. It is accurate to state that the daffodils, which symbolize nature in this poem, provide the author with a sort of companionship. Since "a poet could not be gay, in such a ground company," it keeps him from feeling alone.

THEMES AND ROMANTIC LANGUAGE IN WILLIAM WORDSWORTH'S "THE DAFFODILS":

William Wordsworth writes "The Daffodils" by fusing his descriptive and storytelling abilities. You may hear, see, participate, and form an opinion thanks to the poem's structure. In this sense, it is accurate to state that the poem's form itself facilitates comprehension of the poet's message. The three pretty steady beat rhythms and the gentle, melodic sounds of the rhyming phrases combine to make the poem musical, which is calming and appropriate because the entire poem seems to be dancing, therefore the mood must be gay. This mood is created by the poem's musical nature. Wordsworth highlights this joyful atmosphere with a deft word choice. The phrases streams, golden, fluttering, dancing, tossing, sprightly, jocund, looked, and bliss can all be rethought in this context. Happiness and profound contentment are linked to all of these terms. Each of the poem's four sextet pieces addresses a different facet of the event.

The poem's opening line describes a powerless poet who is aimlessly walking around. Had it not been for his unexpected realization of the daffodils, he would have continued to wander around needless things. This demonstrates how nature is an agent of order. Throughout the poem, God is implied rather than explicitly stated. The daffodils have been "placed" under the trees and next to the lake. The positioning of the daffodils under the trees is essential since they must thrive while avoiding excessive exposure to the blazing sun. It demonstrates how the God of providence is manifest in the natural world.

CONCLUSION

As a romantic, William Wordsworth argues that the mind is liberated from the upheaval of its own negative feelings via a relationship with nature. William Wordsworth believed that whatever that remained in the mind's acquired calmness was the outcome of its association with nature. Man obtains the necessary delight and contentment when he embraces nature and its beauty. Readers could experience the fantasy of a mystical life and a return to nature through William Wordsworth's poetry. appreciating the idea that romanticism promotes of pursuing a life so remote from the stresses of civilization and so near to nature.

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